

Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics surrounding the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 7 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic Financial Institutions

Introduction

The Indonesian Ulema Council (MUI) formed the National Sharia Council (DSN) to help coordinate ulama in responding to economic and financial issues. DSN is expected to be a driver of Islamic teachings in aspects of the national economy and have a role in responding to developments in Indonesian society in the economic and financial fields.

Islamic Financial Institutions need independent institutions that understand sharia principles and have knowledge of Islamic Financial institutions to monitor compliance with these principles. The obligation to comply with sharia principles is regulated in Law no. 21 of 2008 concerning Islamic Financial institutions. The DSN authority contained in the MUI has the authority to form a Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) to supervise the regulations of Islamic Financial institutions.

The existence of DPS in Islamic Financial Institutions is part of efforts to increase public trust in Islamic financial institutions. DPS is tasked with supervising Islamic Financial institutions in all their operational activities, so that Islamic Financial institutions can run in accordance with Islamic sharia. DPS is part of efforts to increase public trust in Islamic Financial institutions. The main function of DPS is to operate Islamic Financial institutions so that

they always comply with Islamic regulations. In addition, DPS must make regular reports that the sharia institutions being supervised are running in accordance with Islamic sharia.

Scientific publications regarding DPS have increased every year. On the Digital Reference Guard (Garuda) website there are 187 studies related to DPS. This shows that research on DPS is quite popular.

According to Rosadah (2012) in the results of her research on the role of the Sharia Product Supervision Supervisory Board in BPRS Amanah Ummah, the organizational structure of BPRS Amanah Ummah shows that BPRS Amanah Ummah is supervised by the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS). DPS has a very important role in supervising sharia aspects at BPRS Amanah Ummah. As a sharia supervisor, it is the duty of the DPS to carry out supervision so that BPRS Amanah Ummah can always be maintained and managed in accordance with sharia principles. This institution is ultimately responsible for the correctness of these practices. Guidelines regarding the duties, authority and responsibilities of the DPS BPRS Amanah Ummah refer to the DPS Fatwa Guidelines.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions using library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Based on DSN decision letter no. 3 of 2000, DPS is part of the Islamic Financial institution concerned, whose placement is approved by DSN. DPS has the authority to supervise the implementation of DSN decisions in Islamic Financial institutions. Based on DSN recommendations through the GMS, DPS are appointed and dismissed at Islamic Financial institutions. DSN recommends DPS members who are competent in the field of sharia to issue a fatwa on Islamic Financial products and services of a national nature so that it can be used as a common reference for DPS.

Islamic Financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit *riba* (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Islamic Financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of Islamic Financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Islamic Financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, Islamic Financial inclusion also supports the development of the Islamic

Financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research. The object of the research is the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) at Islamic Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference

Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then searching for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Council Sharia Supervisory Board " and " Sharia Supervisory Board " throughout the year (2008-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics, methods, research findings and research space based on library research.

Results and Discussion

This chapter will discuss research mapping regarding the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) using VOSviewer bibliometric studies and Library Research studies. Based on search results via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba), publication data was obtained in the form of articles totaling 144 titles originating from accredited national journals.

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions

Search results for scientific publications regarding DPS on Islamic Financial Institutions from 2008 to 2022 shows an increase in publications every year, especially in 2021 with the publication of 35 articles.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2008	1	2014	12	2019	22
2009	1	2015	11	2020	30
2010	3	2016	11	2021	35
2012	3	2017	16	2022	19
2013	4	2018	22		
Total 144					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, there are 17 affiliates/institutions most involved in the publication of research articles regarding the Sharia Supervisory Board in Islamic Financial Institutions. The SYIRKAH Scientific Studies Journal, Kudus State Islamic College, is the journal publishing institution that publishes the

most research results regarding the Sharia Supervisory Board, namely with a total of 4 articles.

Table 1. Ranking of institutions and journals publishing scientific publications around DPS

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Amount Publication
SHIRKAH	4
Baabu Al-ilmi Journal: Sharia Economics and Banking , Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics , Journal of Exploratory Accounting (JEA)	3
AKTSAR: Journal of Sharia Accounting , Az Zarqa': Journal of Islamic Business Law , Banque Syar': Scientific Journal of Sharia Banking , Diponegoro Journal of Accounting , EQUILIBRIUM , Journal of Islamic Accounting and Finance Research , JOURNAL OF ISLAMIC ACCOUNTING AND FINANCE , Journal of Multiparadigm Accounting , Journal Scientific Islamic Economics , Masharif al-Syariah Journal: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking , Student Online Journal (JOM) in the Field of Economics , Journal of Financial and Accounting Research (JRKA) , RATIO: Indonesian Contemporary Accounting Review	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

In table 3, there is information that of a total of 144 published research articles regarding the Sharia Supervisory Board in Islamic Financial Institutions on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba), the most productive researcher is Akhmad Faozan from UIN Purwokerto with 4 journal articles.

Tab el 2. Researcher productivity around the Sharia Supervisory Board

Researcher	Number of Publications
Akhmad Faozan	4
Ermawati L, Anggraini N	3
Mediawati E, Afyana I, Anggadini S, Nugraha Prihutama, Hisyam Faturrahman, Abdul Aziz, Azizah JNR E, Herawati, Rawi, Destina R, Elwardah K, Khayati M, Fadilah Devi, Ariastuti Rahmah, Indriyani, Bekti Ayu, Fatmawati D, Usnan U, Ani Faujiah, Firdaus Edfan, Indrawati Indra, Darlis Novita, Ahmad Furqon, Gary Gagarin, Hasibuan Fuadi, Syahputra Ahmad Fauzul Hakim, Fuadi Angga, Bagas Heradhyaksa, Hikmah Ulfi Kartika Liatul, Oktaviana, Haniah Ilhami, Syukri Iska, Istikomah, Izzatika Ahmad Tarmidzi, Nadia Farhana Lubis, Salimul Jihad, Mohammad Aniq Kamiludin, Fatma Khalieda, Kholiq Hasan Iin Emy, Triono Moh. Abdul, Dwi Condro Prastiwi, Lambey Herman, Mokoginta Linda, Karamoy, Rena Mustari, Sukma Lesmana Lufriansyah, Sayu Mainingsih	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding Sharia Supervisory Boards in Islamic Financial Institutions

Search results on the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) produced 144 research articles regarding the Sharia Supervisory Board at Islamic Financial Institutions in Indonesia. Then, the article is downloaded in RIS (Research Information) format System) is then input and analyzed using VOSViewer, resulting in the following results:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding the Sharia Supervisory Board in Islamic Financial Institutions

Source: Data processed using VOSViewer 1.6.18 software.

the network visualization map of research developments regarding the Sharia Supervisory Board in Islamic Financial Institutions are divided into 4 clusters and 227 topics. The following are the results of the analysis of the bibliometric mapping distribution:

- Cluster 1. The red color consists of 90 topics, namely: according, activity, addition, advice, article, aspect, basis, bmt, book, bprs, business activity, case study, challenge, competence, customer, data collection technique, data source, development, distribution, documentation, dps supervision, dsn, dsn mui, duty, effectiveness, existence, extension, fact, fatwa, field, field research, financial institution, financing, form, function, fund, implementation, improvement, indication, institution, interest, interview, Islamic financial institute, Islamic law, Islamic sharia, keywords, kspps, lack, law, library research, management, manager, mechanism, member, national sharia board, obstacle, operation, operational activity, optimizing the role of god, part, party, person, practice, primary data, principle, problem, product, provision, qualitative approach, regulation,

research, research method, role, rule, sharia, sharia banking, Islamic Financial institute, sharia principle, sharia supervisory board, sharium, supervision, supervisor, system, technique, term, thing, time, type, work.

- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 87 topics, namely: analysis, annual report, assets, audit committee, sharia commercial bank, board, characteristics, commissioner, company, company size, csr, data, data analysis, data analysis technique, board of commissioners, director, disclosure, effect, employee, facto, r financial performance, financial services author, financial statement, frequency, hypothesis, impact, independence, independence, independent commissioner, indonesia, indonesian, influence, institutional ownership, intellectual capital, Islamic bank, Islamic banking, Islamic commercial bank, Islamic social reporting disclosure, Islamic social reporting, ISR, level, leverage, measurement, multiple linear regression, multiple linear regression analysis, multiple regression analysis, number, object, observation, panel data regression, paper, path analysis, performance, period, population, positive effect, profit, profitability, purposive sampling, purposive sampling method, purposive sampling technique, quality, quantitative approach, relationship, report, return, roa, sample, sampling technique, secondary data, sharia bank, sharia commercial bank, sharia supervisory board, sharia supervisory board meeting, significant effect, significant influence, significant positive effect, size, social performance, spss, ssb, ssb member, study, size of sharia supervisory board, variable, year, zakat.
- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 37 topics, namely: banks, Indonesian banks, sharia banks, bpr, compliance, in, and, and sharia supervisory board, data collection method, supervisory board, sharia supervisory board, national sharia board, directors, dps, gcg, good corporate governance, keywords, institution, Iks, method, ojk, financial services authority, in, this research, this research aims, the role of the sharia supervisory board, sharia banking, sharia principles, sharia principles, so, sharia compliance, sharia compliance sharia.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 13 topics, namely: application, authority, conventional bank, effort, extent, indicators, Islamic principles, PBI, position, power, questionnaire, responsibility, supervisory board.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions

Library Research in previous research journals, the researchers found 7 topics related to the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions, namely:

First, DPS according to the banking legal system. The Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions has relevance to the sharia banking legal system. The following are several things that need to be considered when supervising bank operations by DPS. DPS must ensure that the operations, transactions and business of Islamic Financial institutions are carried out in accordance with the rules and principles of Islamic sharia. DPS must have adequate competence in the fields of sharia and Islamic finance in order to better understand and supervise the operations, transactions and business of Islamic Financial institutions. DPS must have sufficient

independence so that it is not dependent on the management of Islamic Financial institutions and is not influenced by economic factors such as fees. DPS must have good transparency and accountability so that DPS reports and supervision results can be accessed by the public and can be accounted for. DPS must collaborate with other supervisory institutions such as the hisbah supervisory institution and the National Sharia Council (DSN) to strengthen supervision of the operations, transactions and business of Islamic Financial institutions. In the sharia banking legal system, DPS has a role and function as a supervisor in the economic activities of Islamic Financial institutions in Indonesia. Therefore, DPS must carry out proper supervision in order to ensure that the operations, transactions and business of Islamic Financial institutions are carried out in accordance with the rules and principles of Islamic sharia.

Second, the role of DPS in sharia banking (Sharia Compliance Supervisory Authority), Sharia Insurance Institutions, Sharia Microfinance Institutions/LKMS, Sharia Rural Banks/BPRS, Sharia Financing Savings and Loans Cooperatives/KSPPS, leasing institutions, sharia capital markets, and Baitul Mal wa Tamwil/BMT.

Third, the influence of DPS on disclosure of zakat fund reports, disclosure of Islamic Social Responsibility / ISR, Corporate Social Responsibility / CSR, disclosure of environmental aspects, performance of Maqashid Syariah, decision to cancel contracts, implementation of contracts, earnings management, achievement of sharia compliance / enforcement of sharia principles, implementation of Good Corporate Governance /GCG, quality of financial reporting, legal violations, earnings management, distribution of ZIS, company performance (independence and professionalism), profitability, financing risk, sharia governance, operational supervision, Return On Deposit/ ROD, banking products/services, supervision of financing contracts, audit report lag, disclosure of accountability, supervision of Rahn products, responsibility for securities crowdfunding, disclosure of Supervisory Board reports, banking tax avoidance behavior, company reputation, healthy banking system, zakat expenditure, risk taking behavior, level of financial soundness (characteristics), financial performance, notarial financing deed, voluntary disclosure, effectiveness of raising funds, effectiveness of financing, Non-Performing Financing/ NPF/financing problems/congestion, development of the halal tourism industry, determination of Murabahah margins, and profit-sharing based financing (competence and model organizing).

Fourth, supervision mechanisms, performance, position, institutions (nomenclature aspects), authority, profile, roles, characteristics, issues, challenges, competencies, functions and problems of DPS.

Fifth, revitalize DPS in sharia economic institutions. Revitalization of the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions can be carried out with the following steps: Increasing the competency of DPS members in the fields of sharia and Islamic finance so that they can better understand and supervise the operations, transactions and business of Islamic Financial institutions. Increase the independence of DPS by ensuring that DPS members are not dependent on the management of Islamic Financial institutions and are not influenced by economic factors such as fees. Increase transparency and accountability of DPS by ensuring that reports and results of DPS supervision can be accessed by the public and can be accounted for. Increase cooperation between DPS and other supervisory institutions such as the hisbah supervisory institution and the National Sharia Council (DSN) to strengthen supervision of the operations, transactions and business of Islamic Financial institutions. By

revitalizing DPS, it is hoped that it can increase the credibility and trust of the public in Islamic Financial institutions and ensure that the operations, transactions and business of these financial institutions are carried out in accordance with the rules and principles of Islamic sharia.

Sixth, the relevance of the hisbah supervisory institution to DPS. The Hisbah Supervisory Institution and the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions have relevance in supervising the operations, transactions and business of these financial institutions which are carried out in accordance with the rules and principles of Islamic sharia. Based on research results, Hisbah is a supervisory institution that has existed since the time of the Prophet, and supervision is carried out directly at the scene of the crime, minimizing crimes that occur in the market. The Hisbah supervisory institution has the main function of supervising and instructing people to do good and avoid evil, especially in the economic sector, which more or less occurs in the market. In Indonesia there are also modern economic supervision institutions such as BPOM, LPPOM, KPPU, and there is DSN, all of which are engaged in the field of supervision. DPS is a unit owned by a company/organization that is run according to Islamic sharia. DPS is responsible for ensuring that the operations, transactions and business of the financial institution are carried out in accordance with the rules and principles of Islamic sharia. DPS has a role and function as a supervisor in the economic activities of Islamic Financial institutions in Indonesia. Even though Hisbah and DPS have differences in function and specifications, they both have the same main task, namely supervising the economic sector in particular from 3 aspects, namely production, distribution and consumption. Therefore, DPS can study and pay attention to Hisbah's experience in economic supervision and apply it to the supervision of operations, transactions and business of Islamic Financial institutions.

Seventh, the influence of fees and religiosity on DPS independence. In the context of Islamic Financial Institutions, the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) is a unit owned by a company/organization that is run in accordance with Islamic sharia. DPS is responsible for ensuring that the operations, transactions and business of the financial institution are carried out in accordance with the rules and principles of Islamic sharia. In research conducted to analyze the influence of economic factors and religiosity on the independence of DPS in Islamic Financial Institutions, it was found that economic factors and religiosity influence the independence of DPS. There is a possibility for Islamic bank management to place more emphasis on economic aspects rather than religious aspects. Several economic dimensions that are thought to influence the independence of DPS are that DPS will depend on management so they tend to be reluctant to oppose the will/desires of management, and if they do not provide reports that are in accordance with management's wishes, DPS members will feel worried about losing their jobs considering the relative income they receive. big. From the results of this research, it can be concluded that economic factors and religiosity influence the independence of DPS in Islamic Financial Institutions. Therefore, it is necessary to have strict and independent supervision of the DPS in order to ensure that the operations, transactions and business of the financial institution are carried out in accordance with the rules and principles of Islamic sharia.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 7 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions.

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